

MAIN NON-CONFORMITIES FOUND BY THE ASSESSMENT THE HABILITATION OF PRE AND POST COVID-19 HOSPITALS

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Abstract

Purpose - To identify the main pre and post COVID-19 non-conformities in ensuring and continuously improving the quality of health services and patient safety following the evaluation of hospitals through standardization.

Methodology/approach - For this exploratory study we used the policy and regulatory framework for quality assurance of bed-based health facilities, as well as publicly and directly available data from the National Health Quality Management Authority, research tools evaluation and monitoring checklists for a category of quality indicators, mainly targeting direct observation checklist indicators, efficiency and effectiveness indicators, monitoring indicators and critical indicators, the latter allowing the evaluation committee to interrupt the visit when identified. We analysed the available data and information focusing on the whole system. We surveyed 285 accredited health units out of a total of 675 health units registered in the accreditation process and 94 health units monitored in the thematic monitoring process, for the direct monitoring visit and the majority of health units through self-assessment.

Findings - Non-compliant indicators from the assessment process were predominantly indicators that are prevalent on the direct observation lists. I mention here indicators related to: age of buildings, inadequate infrastructure, retrogressions, facilities for people with disabilities, circuits and transport. In general, structural changes require large investments, so changes in mentality and improved information circuits between different services and units, through information sharing and group work apprenticeships, are essential.

Research limitations/implications - The research does not cover all hospitals under evaluation in the second accreditation cycle, as this cycle runs until 2023. During the state of emergency, evaluation and monitoring visits were stopped and monitoring tools were not used. Monitoring includes surveys during the state of alert. Self-assessment was carried out for most health facilities, but monitoring through monitoring visits was carried out only in 94 health facilities.

Practical implications - Monitoring led to the use of procedures, protocols for limiting the increase in O₂ concentration. The questionnaires used were those from the thematic monitoring of the National Health Quality Management Authority. Data analysis reiterated the need to implement quality management not only at the declarative level but also at the system level. The data used were data from the National Authority for Quality Management in Health.

Originality/value - To the best of our knowledge, there is no integrated management system at the level of health facilities, there is no methodology available to decrease the failure rate of continuous improvement projects, providing a "roadmap", a clear traceability for the use of quality management systems approach. The analysis and study on pre and post CoVID-19 accreditation and monitoring in Romanian hospitals has not been carried out.

Key words: quality, accreditation of health facilities, monitoring, pandemic, quality culture, monitoring indicators.

Introduction

Patient safety has been a worrying issue in the Romanian healthcare system in recent years, reflecting international trends. Updating the regulations and procedures for the assessment, accreditation and monitoring of healthcare, hospital and ambulatory care providers in Romania aims to promote patient safety and quality healthcare services. One component that has received special attention recently is the monitoring of healthcare facilities. Accreditation of health care units is the process of validating the conformity of the characteristics of health care services performed by health care units with the accreditation standards adopted by National Authority for Quality Management in Health Care and approved under the terms of this law, as a result of which health care units are classified into accreditation categories to confer confidence in their technical-professional and organizational competence [1]. Health facility assessment is the activity of analysing the level of compliance of health facilities with accreditation standards, carried out by external health service assessors, independent of stakeholders, when health facilities request to enter the accreditation procedure. [1] National Authority for Quality Management in Health Care accreditation is a cyclical process that takes place every 5 years, the current accreditation cycle, the second, will end in 2023. During the 5 years of validity of the accreditation certificate, the monitoring process of the accredited units takes place, with the aim of supporting these units in maintaining the conditions on the basis of which they have obtained the accreditation, but also in implementing new solutions that contribute to the continuous improvement of the quality of health services and patient safety.

Thematic monitoring can be an alternative to evaluation, to continuous improvement of medical activity, and to the implementation of accreditation standards. It is an essential pre- and post-accreditation process that aims to ensure that hospitals are continually concerned with maintaining and improving the quality of service provided and patient safety. It has a proactive, and supportive role. The study shows how hospitals had to adapt to an unprecedented situation **SARS-CoV-2 pandemic** in a very short time. Structures and services were reorganised, human resources were adapted, the necessary equipment was provided, new procedures were developed and implemented, and new facilities were developed. All hospitals were sent detailed explanations of the monitoring topics for which self-assessment of related risks was required: patient admission, workplace safety and security, equipment and facility safety. From the totality of hospitals only 7 hospitals did not communicate the data set, to which ART. 3 of ANMCS ordinance no. 433/2020 was applied. A minimum of 2 hospitals, which were randomly selected, both public and private, COVID wards and non-COVID wards, from each county, were subject to research in the thematic monitoring phase I in February 2021 according to the thematic monitoring visits for field validation of data. 89 public hospitals and 5 private hospitals, divided by category (Table 1). These topics covered many current aspects of running a bed-based health facility. For example: reporting adverse events associated with healthcare, waste management, etc., but also issues arising from one-off circumstances, preparing units for the reception of patients with COVID-19 or suspects, assessing units after adverse events, how bedded health units are prepared to respond to disasters.

Table 1. Hospitals that received the February 2021 thematic monitoring visit

a) Category I - very high level of competence:	6
<i>aa) category I</i>	3
<i>ab) category I M</i>	3
b) Category II - high level of competence:	19
<i>ba) category II</i>	10
<i>bb) category II M</i>	9
c) Category III - medium level of competence:	32
d) Category IV - basic competence level:	32
e) Category V - limited level of competence:	5

Data on the use of O₂ facilities, (Fig 2), employee route and patient route, occupational burnout syndrome, pandemic communication adaptation, and fire safety and security were analyzed. From the analysis, we found that the health care facilities conducted staff training on the prohibition of the use of flammable materials in rooms where patients with continuous O₂ therapy are admitted and the handling of incompatible substances to react exothermally with O₂ at concentration above the alarm threshold in 56.4% (Fig. 3). Although O₂ itself is non-flammable, it promotes combustion and allows all flammable materials to burn much more vigorously; the risk is all the greater because O₂ is odourless and can only be detected by specific sensors. Therefore, the lack of continuous monitoring of the O₂ concentration in the air in medical premises may favour its increase above a certain value (22.5 - 23%) and represents a major risk in the occurrence of fires even from a simple spark. The risk can be reduced by better ventilation.

Status of the indicator from the perspective of self-assessment by 646 USP

Situation of the indicator in 94 self-assessed sanitary units and subsequently, the finding in the field

Fig. 2. The locations where the O₂ concentration must be monitored are identified

Status of the indicator from the perspective of self-assessment by 646 USP

The status of the indicator from the perspective of self-assessment and, subsequently, the finding in the field of 94 USP

Fig. 3. Health Units that have carried out staff training on the prohibition of the use in rooms where patients are hospitalized with continuous O₂ therapy of flammable materials and the handling of incompatible substances to react exothermally with O₂ at a concentration above the alarm threshold

The International Joint Recommendations on Medical Electrical Safety specify that, at ambient pressure, the O₂ concentration in the air in medical premises should not exceed a certain value, and the warning and avoidance of such a dangerous situation is done by continuous monitoring by O₂ sensors. Declared by self-assessment on the specific National Authority for Quality Management in Health Care platform, 68.3% of the monitored health units (441 out of 646) confirm the identification of premises requiring O₂ concentration monitoring, while 5.7%, 37 out of 646 did not identify these premises, and for 26% 168 out of 646 health units the indicator does not apply the medical services offered in these units do not require O₂ installation. Staff training contributes, together with O₂ concentration monitoring, to reducing the risk of fire corresponding to O₂ concentration above the safe limit in the premises where it is used. Staff should also be aware of the frequency with which they should ventilate the premises if there is no automatic air ventilation system. For the employee route and the patient route, we found differences between the statements made by the health facilities and the findings made during the monitoring visits (Fig. 4) and (Fig. 5). Triage contributes to reducing the infectious risk as a result of highlighting the possibility of germ carriage from staff to patient or staff to staff. Prompt confirmation of the suspected case is necessary to ensure rapid and effective epidemiological surveillance of contacts, implementation of infection prevention and control measures and collection of epidemiological and clinical information. If a patient or staff member presents with specific signs and symptoms according to the case definition, it is recommended to apply infection-specific measures. Separation of pathways without intersecting at any point together with epidemiological triage of staff contributes substantially to reducing the infectious risk to the patient. At the time of the online self-assessment, 81.9%, 528 out of the total of 646 health facilities reported having separate circuits for suspected COVID-19 patients. As a result of the monitoring visits, the percentage of these units decreased to 58.5%, 55 out of 94 health units visited, with the causes of invalidation including: crossing of circuits mostly at elevator level, deletion of markings or non-compliance.

Fig. 4. Staff access ways are separate from patient access

The analysis of the monitoring of burnout syndrome presents the status of the indicator from the perspective of self-assessment by 646 health facilities. The health units defined alarm indicators related to the occurrence of burnout syndrome, reveals according to (Fig. 6) the existence of a difference between the self-assessed 646 health units and the health units where the indicator was found 94 health units. The screening - diagnosis - solutions professional exhaustion is a recent concern in the Romanian healthcare system, although the signs of this phenomenon appeared before the COVID-19 pandemic, and became more pronounced during its duration. Most of the time, the concern for this phenomenon has been limited and sometimes confused with the evaluation of employee satisfaction.

The study on the indicator: the health facility has a fire safety permit for all buildings reveals that (Fig. 7) for the sub-theme: safety and security in case of fire of the total number of assessed health facilities 57.3% had a negative response to the self-assessment, compared to 73.4% found for the 94 health facilities where monitoring visits were made. Safety and security in case of fire, the indicator analysed "the sectors of activity of the health unit are organised in such a way as to allow evacuation in case of

emergency by at least two routes" was found according to (Fig. 8) that 57.4% of the health units allow evacuation by two routes. The existence and knowledge of the staff of at least two escape routes is verified, the lift not being considered as an escape route, which is also properly signposted 24/7. Declaratively, 85% of health facilities (549/646) confirm that they are properly organised for the situation.

Fig. 5. Access ways for staff are provided with triage points.

Fig. 5.1. There are separate circuits for patients declared suspicious after triage

The percentage of self-reporting is reconfirmed among the hospitals monitored in the field, 85.1%, respectively 80/94 health units and found in 57.4% health units (54/94); the difference is justified by the fact that not all sectors of activity have this facility related to evacuation. The existence of an alternative source of O₂ decreases the risk of complications and even death in patients dependent on oxygen therapy. 62.9% of all hospitals (406/646 health facilities) reported the existence of alternative solutions for oxygen therapy. Visits to 94 hospitals showed that such solutions exist in 71 of them (75.5%). Exceeding the rated capacity is a major risk that can lead to automatic power cut-off, fuses tripped on overload or a fire. The use of extension cords or other temporary devices carries the risk of overloading the power grid and blocking access routes, or preventing staff and patients from moving around. A fire in a hospital can start from a variety of causes, with a much greater risk in areas where O₂ is

administered for therapeutic purposes; the source of a fire can be a short circuit or a faulty connection to a mobile phone, radio, air heater.

Fig. 6. Syndr monitoring. of "professional exhaustion" ("burn-out") The health unit has defined alarm indicators related to the installation of the exhaustion syndrome.

Fig. 7. The sanitary facility has a fire safety permit for all buildings

Fig. 8. The activity sectors of the health unit are organized in such a way that they allow emergency evacuation by at least two routes

Discussion and conclusions

The monitoring of the health units in Romania showed real progress during the period under review, supported by improvements in the policy and regulatory framework, their adaptation from the start and learning from mistakes. We found an increasing number of patients requiring high flow oxygen. Wards that were not designed for such therapy, lacking room ventilation facilities of min. 6 volumes/hour, are having to take on such patients. It is necessary that the hospital management is permanently connected with the situation of these wards, in order to be able to apply risk mitigation measures, continuous monitoring of O₂ concentration in the air, specific trainings for staff. The existence of back-up solutions requires the involvement of the guardian authority, respectively the **Ministry of Health**, the Local Council, the County Council, in order to ensure the continuity of O₂ supply to patients in case of failure, to eliminate the risk of continuing to use a plant when failures occur: the plant can thus be shut down, repaired and then restarted and to eliminate the risks of "improvisation" to repair failures in a plant that could not be shut down. The value added by monitoring analysis is:

- awareness of all stakeholders on various key issues;
- opportunity to identify, with professionalism and honesty, other problems;
- not a process to tick off, but to trigger corrections, identify causes and improve;
- a cooperative process between Health Units and the National Authority for Quality Management in Health;
- shows us "Where are we? and What more to do?".

The Socratic tradition of our medicine is based on medical competence and skill and techniques acquired in the field, in contact with other professionals belonging to the same body. Interdisciplinary encounters should lead to treating the patient as a system not as a disease in which clinical governance predominates. Instruction and information can no longer be kept or spread stingily by some who assume power over the exclusivity of their science. When it is written down, teaching is easy to transmit.

The **SARS-CoV-2 pandemic** has tested the resilience of the healthcare system and beyond to an unprecedented situation. Healthcare facilities have had very little time to prepare, to reorganise their services, to train staff, to develop effective ways to motivate employees and care for patients safely. The response to this situation has brought unprecedented transformations, implemented by most hospitals in a relatively short time. During this period, the equipping of health units with specific and much-needed equipment has taken place at a rapid pace and, above all, in line with the immediate needs identified. New working procedures have also been adopted in hospitals in a short time and interest in telemedicine services has increased.

Despite the progress made by health facilities on several fronts, the following issues remain uncovered:

- (i) burnout with the highest rate of negative responses,
- (ii) separation of patient and staff circuits,
- (iii) fire preparedness, a red flag being the lack of fire safety authorisation and the reduced capacity to evacuate people from rooms,
- (iv) safe use of oxygen therapy,
- (v) inadequate conditions for the use of electrical installations with outdated installations with improvised extensions, combined with a lack of real-time control of their functionality.

A fire in a hospital can start from a variety of causes, with the risk being much higher in areas where O₂ is administered for therapeutic purposes. The source of the fire could be a short circuit, a faulty connection to a mobile phone, radio or air conditioner.

Remedial measures found from the study were used to develop their own checklists/monitoring tools. Reactive measures become proactive, through unannounced visits to hospitals where improvements were noted post National Authority for Quality Management in Health monitoring, but also other issues noted on an ad hoc basis: non-completion of cleaning charts, worn linen, lack of pillows or blankets, deficiencies in waste collection, bins without lids, staff wearing jewellery. Responsibilities that were concentrated in the hands of a few, today need to be disseminated in a controlled way. The implementation of procedures and protocols is quite difficult, the transition from oral to written culture faces existential but not impossible difficulties.

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